

Supplementary Figure 6. Chord diagram showing the DEGs of *exo70B2* seedlings (compared to WT control) found to associate with several selected GO categories pathways (on the right). The color code of the fold change of genes' expression is shown on the right.

Supplementary Figure 7. Chord diagram showing the DEGs of *exo70BlxB2* seedlings (compared to WT control) found to associate with several selected GO categories (on the right). The color code of the fold change of genes' expression is shown on the left.